

JUPITER TRANSIT AND MARRIAGE

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Abstract:

Gochara is as important as our own horoscope. The planets are moving every day. This is called planetary transit. When we look at the horoscope, the result is Gochara Palangal depending on the planetary system located. Based on Astrology weekly rasiphalan, monthly rasipalan are said based on this planetary transit. Among Nine Planets the transit of Jupiter, Saturn, Rahu-Ketu is mainly considered, because these planets take more than a year to move from one zodiac sign to the next. The impact of Jupiter's transit created to a person's marriage is analyzed in this article.

Key Words: Jupiter, Planetary Transit, Gochara Palangal, Natal Moon, Zodiac Sign, Marriage, Happiness, Partner, Beneficiary Positions of Jupiter's Transit.

Introduction:

Generally, one doubt that all astrological enthusiasts have is whether everything that happens in our life is happening according to their Dasa Buddhi times or according to planetary transit. Apart from this doubt, many people have many questions about what is planetary transit, what is Dasa Buddhi, how to see the benefits of a planetary transit, which creates confusion about what will give the right result and what will work. In the case of a horoscope, the planetary transit will be different and the Dasa Buddhi will be different. So, when you look at what works exactly, both will work. In fact, the two are one and the same. That is, there are many methods of astrology. But all methods bring the same result.

An Introduction to Jupiter:

Jupiter brings a person a new growth in his life, transformation, new insights, learning, blessings, & success during its transit. So, in this phase, it's best to focus on making some positive changes in different areas of the person's life. The person will see a new growth in his life. Whether it is financial growth, increase in debt or health related issues, all things start getting increased, depending on the house in which Jupiter is transiting. Jupiter's transit gives the person success in personal and professional life by providing him a better knowledge over a concerned matter. But a retrograde Jupiter during transit can weaken his decision-making ability and lack happiness in the relationship. Jupiter plays a significant role to cause transformation in life with new insights, learning, blessings, success and growth in its transit period. Jupiter transits one zodiac sign for nearly one year. Jupiter signifies major areas of life including growth, satisfaction, love, health, family, and support from children and harmony in marital life. So, during the transit of Jupiter, the person needs to focus on making some positive changes in different areas of his life to get happiness and prosperity. When Jupiter is in debilitated form during its transit, it will give him hidden insights about overcoming challenges with a practical and determined approach.

Jupiter's Transit Creating Impacts in Life:

- The person will enjoy his relationship with family, spouse, friends, & siblings. Transit of Jupiter will also give him support of his family members and near & dear ones.
- The person may crave for his favourite cuisine, and he will get that as a surprise from one of his family members.
- Guidance from senior and elder will help the person in making correct decisions during this transit period.
- The person will enjoy a monetary gain during the transit period of Jupiter. He will make long-term secure investments.
- On professional front, salary increment is indicated, and he will use his income in making investments in the right fund.
- The person will get name, fame and recognition of his good deeds in society.

Transformation of Life:

- Opportunities are on the way through which the person can learn new things that will help in his overall betterment. The person should respect the opportunities as ignorance can cause lack of knowledge and growth.
- The person will see a new growth in his finances. There will be a new addition in his family through a childbirth or a marriage. During this transit, he will be in pink of his health, happy, and feel younger than his age, thanks to its antioxidant energy.
- The person will see a positive changes in his habit and adapt a healthy daily routine. His positive approach towards problems will give him strength to solve them.
- Jupiter will help the person in realizing his feelings, necessities & wishes. This clarity will help him to build a good understanding and strong bonding with his partner.
- Jupiter will bless the person with scholarship, higher study and enrolled for higher study abroad. Jupiter's energy will give him the ability to filter the information and transform them into wisdom to execute his plan. This will help in good growth and transformation in professional life.

Gocharam:

Gocharam is a current planetary transit. Gocharam of the planets is determined from the natal moon sign. Gocharam should also be analyzed along with the Dasa and antardasa predictions. The Gocharam ortransists of Jupiter, Saturn are extremely important. If the Dasa and antardasa are not favorable, but if the Jupiter and Saturn transits are favorable for entire year, then the

person gets completely protected that year. Gocharam of mercury is very important for predicting the Stock Market trends. Mercury normally retrogrades three times in a year. Mercury retrograde can create lot of turbulence and downward trend in the stock market. However, when it gets combust during the retrogression, the effects of the retrograde will diminish. In other words, the market tends to get better. When the mercury is out of retrograde, the markets normally stabilize. If a horoscope is analyzed with Gochara transit of planets along with the Dasa and antardasa, the predictions will be more accurate. Here are some examples: If a person is struggling for a job and dasa and antardasa are moderately favorable, then look if the Sun is placed in third, sixth, tenth, or eleventh houses in the Gochara and aspected by Jupiter the person will definitely get a job. Similarly, Jupiter or Rahu in twelfth house will easily give foreign travel during that year.

Sometimes, a planet in the Gochara transit may not be able to give full benefic influence, in spite of transiting a favorable house in Gochara. This is due to obstruction of some other planet. This is called Gochara Vedha. The Gochara Vedha can diminish the positive effects of a particular planet during that transit. For example, when Jupiter is transiting the second house, he gives very favorable results, but there is some other planet in the twelfth house from the natal moon, then positive effects of Jupiter's second house transit from the natal moon are diminished. The extent, to which the positive effects can be reduced, varies from a person to person based on the Karmas. So, if there are two people A and B with the same Rasi, and Jupiter is transiting the second house in Gochara. If there is a planet in twelfth house causing Vedha, both the Person A and B will not get the 100% results of Jupiter's benefic transit in second house.

Gochara Predictions for Jupiter (Jupiter Transit):

In astrology, Jupiter is the planet of luck. It is capable of giving good luck, health and abundant wealth. According to the horoscope, if Jupiter is strong in one's birth horoscope, then that person will get permanent results due to the miraculous benefit of Jupiter in any difficult situation. It is customary to fix the day by looking at the strength of the Jupiter while fixing the muhurtham for auspicious activities. Let's know on what basis that Jupiter's strength is determined. The house to which a planet gives its barrels is a strong place for that planet. Based on this, the benefits of Gochara are predicted. According to this, Transit of Jupiter will be strong when he is transiting in second, fifth, seventh, ninth and eleventh houses from the house where Natal Moon is stationed. This is referred to as the strength of the Jupiter.

Transit of Jupiter through Different Houses and its Impact:

According to the study of astrologers, Jupiter is an influential and a benefic planet. It is a planet of knowledge, which has its influence on mind, soul, education, marriage, wealth, etc. Jupiter has different impact on individuals according to its transit in different houses which means bhavas.

Jupiter's Transit through the First House of the Zodiac Sign:

If Jupiter transits through the first house in the birth-chart and an individual is making plans for marriage, then the marriage is definitely on cards. Transit of Jupiter through this house, makes an individual physically and mentally fit. It helps a person achieve success in his work and is economically beneficial for him. It opens new areas of income. It provides respect and honor to an individual in the society as well as success at the work front. Due to the aspect of Jupiter, individual may have increased interest towards spirituality and in social services. In this state, the individual may have a busy schedule in life and considers himself superior to others. Jupiter's transit through the first house may give rise to conflicts in the individual's family life.

The person will enjoy a great bonding with his partner and family. The person will get recognition, name, and fame with the transit of Jupiter in the first house. With a healthy and open conversation with his partner will give him a long-term relationship. The person will get an opportunity to help needy that will give him reputation in the society. The person's honest approach and hard work will give him recognition and success and he will get support of his senior. Jupiter in first house is not favorable. It will bring lot of hurdles and tensions in all aspects of life. There will be delays in all the activities. There will be lack of happiness and satisfactions. However, this period may be good for religious or spiritual purposes. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is not favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Second House of the Zodiac Sign:

Jupiter's transit through the second house makes an individual economically strong. Increase in income can be accompanied by a rise in expenditure. As a result, he may continue to remain mentally disturbed. The individual may also have an impressive and influential personality. He will gain respect and honor in the society and happiness from his children but the overall happiness level from the family will be average. Property related decisions will also be beneficial for him. During this phase the individual will be more inclined towards spirituality and religious work, because Jupiter represents religion. The person may build a good connection with new people who will help him in his financial increment. Transit of Jupiter in second house will bless him with a good health by following a healthy diet. He will get expected outcomes in terms of savings during this transit. There will be an addition in his family with a new baby or marriage-related event. He will be capable of delivering his work before the deadline and this will give him the expected success on the professional front. It will bless the person with the insights to have clarity before making commitment to his partner. This will help in maintaining harmony in his relationship. Jupiter in second house Gochara is very favorable. The person will be bestowed with wealth, good income, and happiness. There can also be a birth in the family. The relation with the family members will be good. If there is a planet in the twelfth house from moon, the Jupiter will be in Vedha. That means, the positive effects of Jupiter will reduce. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is most favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Third House of the Zodiac Sign:

Jupiter's transit in the third house has a positive impact on health, as well as on academics, literature and philosophy. The person's work will be recognized and will speak about his generosity. The person's high thinking will get him respect and honor in his personal and professional life. The person's old friends will also be very supportive. He will get opportunities to meet new people and establish friendly relations with them. Traveling is also possible and will be blissful. The person might not get the recognition or appreciation of his hard work and effort due to the transit of Jupiter in the third house. He should improve his skill and take the initiative to get success in all his endeavours. Transit of Jupiter will bless a person with new skills that give him

success and a good financial income. His creative ideas will help him work on strategy and get promotion, growth and success. The person may meet a people of high position on social media. Follow the guidelines or advice of your mentor, senior or elder. Jupiter is not favorable in the third house in Gochara. There will be lot of hurdles in the person's life. Financially this may not be a good phase. There will be obstacles in business. The person is also likely to lose some money. He may have trouble with his employer. However, some of them may do some religious deeds, because Jupiter will aspect the ninth house. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter may not support for a person to get married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Fourth House of the Zodiac Sign:

If Jupiter transits through the fourth house the person will have good fortune. Happiness and prosperity may flourish in his family life. Due to the arrival of happiness in his life, he may have many expectations. He may be satisfied mentally and will have a healthy body. He will make profits in business and will have good economic status. When Jupiter transits through this house, it means the person's pending projects and assignments will be completed. He may come to a definite decision regarding any vehicle or property. He may get benefits from his in-laws and may fulfill his needs through his intellect and hard work.

Follow a proper ethics to be happy during the transit of Jupiter in fourth house. The person will get good news and happiness in his life. Good habits and support from the family will lead him toward success. The person might work on pending tasks for the completion and make himself ready to accept the new one. Expected deal and benefit will come in his favour with the blessing of Jupiter's transit in the fourth house. Jupiter is not favorable in fourth house in Gochara. This brings along worries for the person. Stay away from any kind of litigations and property related issues. Try and maintain cordial relationships with the person's relatives and friends. Financially this could be a trying time for him. Take measures to avoid unnecessary expenses and travel. Be careful when driving vehicles. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is also not favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Fifth House of the Zodiac Sign:

When Jupiter transits through the fifth house, it provides positive results. Because of its influence, a person may be more inclined towards different areas of knowledge, also in music and writing. The person will be keen to have in-depth study of astrology, philosophy and literature. The person may get attracted and fall in love with the person of opposite sex. Due to the influence of the transit, people who may have the desire to get children will be fulfilled. It is also beneficial for economic matters. The person may get support from the people who may be associated with politics and government. It is a good time for success and promotion in his work. The person will get support and happiness from your children. There will be celebration and happiness in his life with the auspicious movement of Jupiter in the fifth house. The habit of exercising and chanting mantra will bless him with expected transformation during this transit period. If he is expecting a childbirth/pregnancy, then this period will give him happiness. The person's love life will get strengthen during this transit period. He may become successful in getting new projects, growth and promotion. Jupiter is highly favorable in fifth house in Gochara. Financially, this will prove to be a good time. It is also good time for any speculations like stocks. An auspicious event may take place at home, like birth of child. The person may successfully complete all his plans and wishes. If a person is single, he may get perfect match. It is also good time for students too well in their studies. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is highly favorable for a person to get married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Sixth House of the Zodiac Sign:

When Jupiter transits in the sixth house then it gives an average result. The person may get health related problems and mixed effects on his mental status. The person's hard work will help him to get good position in his job or business. His enemies will not face him and will not cause any conflict on the work-front. The person will have economic benefits and an increase in income, although, expenditure will also increase, so, economic balance is the necessity in this situation. However, due to his investments and spending in beneficial and benedictory work he will remain happy and will get family support. The person will get prosperity and accomplishments with his ability to win over opponents. However, it can give expansion in loan and debt-related issues because of his ignorance. During this transit period, the person will realize the value of the financial management. Jupiter's transit in the sixth house will make him capable of delivering tasks on time. Unexpected obstacles in his way will make him realize his true potential. Any litigation related issue will get resolved during this period. Jupiter is not favorable in sixth house in Gochara. The person need pay more attention to his health. There may be lot of expenditure and debts. He may not have cordial relations with his coworkers. He feel unhappy and restless. The person need to be careful with the thieves or any theft. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is not favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Seventh House of the Zodiac Sign:

When Jupiter transits in the seventh house in the person birth chart then it is in a very benefic position. It creates marriage yoga for the unmarried. It will have a good effect on his married life and gives a sweet relationship between husband and wife. It is also beneficial for progeny, which means he will be blessed by children. The person's respect and honor will increase in the society. If he is jobless then he will get a job soon. During this transit he will get success and promotion in his job or business. Economic conditions will improve and he will have many sources of income. The person's expenditure will also get increased but still he will be happy and excited. The person will see expansion in his business by finalizing expected deals. He will get recognition and success of his hard work and efforts at the workplace. Jupiter transits seventh house and it will make him happy with his spouse, however, it also demands commitment and free space in his marital life. The person will get the support of his life partner. The person's family and friends will make him special with their love and care. He may take an interest in study about healing and health-related topics and get inclined towards reading about yoga, healing & meditation. Jupiter is highly favorable in seventh house in Gochara. The person will have lot of happiness and relations with the spouse will also be good. If a person is single, he may get married during this period. He will enjoy good health. The person will have good relations with his coworkers. Socially, this a very good time. He will enjoy the company of friends and relatives. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is most suitable for a person to get married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Eighth House of the Zodiac Sign:

This phase will produce average results. The person will be physically fit but he will be mentally disturbed and unstable due to the effects of the Jupiter's transit in the eighth house. If he do not keep a control on himself then anger and frustration may hamper his peace of mind. Enemies will not try to face the person therefore; he will achieve success in his work. The person will

be appreciated for his work and he will continue to work hard. The person will have a moderate economic status and but may get a surprise source of income. The person will be supported by government and will be successful. The person may face challenges in terms of debt and chronic health issues. He will be capable of making correct financial decisions. With the help of expert's advice, he will get relief from debt and loans. He will start learning from his mistakes and that will help him in making right decision even in challenging situations in life. The person will be capable of finding solutions for all the problems in his life. Transit of Jupiter in eighth house help him in controlling aggression and avoid unlawful deeds. He will get clarity over his doubts on spiritual and religious beliefs, and it will give him peace of mind. The person need to take care of his eating habit to avoid any health issues. Jupiter is not favorable in eighth house in Gochara. There may be unnecessary expenditure and travel is likely to be troublesome. The person may have to work hard in his job to succeed. There may be lack of bodily comforts. The person may have to visit hospitals and health may not be good. He need to be careful with lawsuits and litigations. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is not favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Ninth House of the Zodiac Sign:

When Jupiter's transit is in the ninth house in the person birth chart then it makes him physically and mentally fit. He will be energetic and happy and his all-pending work will be successfully done. He will be inclined towards religion and spirituality. At work front, he will get some new projects which will give him benefits in the future. He may get promotion or new work-related responsibilities in this transit which will be highly beneficial for him. There will be an increase in wealth and he will be respected in the society. The person will enjoy a great bonding with his seniors and elders in his family. An optimistic approach will help him in finding solution of any problem. Higher study or career related foreign travel would be there. Jupiter's transit in ninth house can give him clarity in his thoughts by getting deep into a concerned matter and understand the root cause. The person may meet an intelligent person who will help him in making right decisions. Jupiter is highly favorable in ninth house in Gochara. There will good income and financial gains. The person will show lot of interest in religious activities and he is likely to attend as the religious functions. This period is particularly good time for authors, publishers, professors and people related to the field of books. There is also a possibility of foreign distance travel. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is most favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Tenth House of the Zodiac Sign:

Transit of Jupiter in the tenth house will help the person achieve success at the job front or business. Due to its influence, he will have good relations with the people from politics and of government which will help him to reap benefits in life. There will be peace in the family and he will have a great married life during this transit. He will get benefic results regarding money and wealth. Due to the influence of Jupiter's transit, respect and honor in the society will increase. The person will achieve success in his work through your hard work and dedication. The person should work hard and put in more effort rather than focusing on expected rewards. During the transit period of Jupiter in tenth house, his colleague and boss will support him. The person clarity towards his work will give him success on professional front. This transit may cause the person dream large and become more optimistic which should be avoided. A realistic and practical approach help him in achieving his goal. Jupiter is not favorable in tenth house in Gochara. The person may develop negative thinking and a feeling of wretchedness during this time. Some unfulfilled desires may make the person irritable as well. Avoid wandering about, as the person is most likely to be disappointed during this particular time. This is the time when he needs to consciously avoid arguments with his seniors at work and with his elders at home. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is not favorable for a person to get married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Eleventh House of the Zodiac Sign:

When Jupiter transits in the eleventh house, the economic conditions become strong. The person will get new sources of income which will be economically beneficial for him. This period may get him success in business or if he is doing a job then his position would become stronger. The person may also get a promotion in his job. He will have a busy schedule due to the heavy workload. The person's respect and honor in the society will increase and mentally he will be happy and satisfied. If the person is waiting for the financial upliftment, then he will get increment during this period. A polite and positive approach will rise his status and respect in his social circle. During Jupiter's transit in eleventh house, he may start taking an interest in building a strong social relationship. The person's long-awaited desire will get fulfilled. The person will enjoy success in his love life by tying the knot of marriage with his partner. Jupiter is favorable in eleventh house in Gochara. This signifies a good time. During this time, the person may expect promotions at the workplace, gain in trade and even a position of higher authority in his professional life. This could also prove to be a socially good time for him, as the person's status in the society is likely to be heightened. Finances would be good and most of them would consider buying landed property, jewelry, new vehicles and acquiring material comfort in this time. He would also enjoy sound health and a peaceful mind. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is most favorable for getting married.

Jupiter's Transit through the Twelfth House of the Zodiac Sign:

When Jupiter's transit is in the twelfth house then the person's physical and mental fitness will remain average. The person may sometimes fall sick but there is no possibility of a serious malady. His mental status will also be at comfortable level but sometimes he may get tense and restless. Jupiter's transit gives him benefits in money matters but he will always be prepared to invest in the benedictory work. The person will achieve success in his work but he have to work hard for achievements in his life. During this period, there are possibilities for traveling which will definitely have future benefits. The person's hard work will win him respect and honor in the society. The person may face unexpected health-related expenses, so he need to work on a priority-based plan rather than getting extravagant. There will be a foreign connection or transformation in his thought with a spiritual inclination during this transit of Jupiter in twelfth house. During this period, he may experience a positive transformation in his subconscious thoughts that will help in improving his personality. There might be sudden expenses on family get together and meeting old friends, so a priority-based plan will help you enjoying such moments with his near and dear ones rather than getting into financial crunch. Jupiter is not favorable in twelfth house in Gochara. This indicates expenditure for the person. The outflow of money is expected to be greater than the inflow. Above all, he may also find difficulty in trade and business, especially related to the cattle business. However, he also likely to spend some money on auspicious occasions and on long distance travels.

This period may force upon him a phase in which he may have to stay away from his native place and away from his children. If employed, hold on to his position and rank at work as this period may put a risk to these as well. In marriage aspect, this planetary position of Jupiter is not favorable for getting married.

Conclusion:

If a person wants to get married it is very important to know the planetary position of transit Jupiter. The most favorable planetary position of the Transit Jupiter from the zodiac sign to get married is second, fifth, seventh, ninth, eleventh positions. Unfavorable planetary position of the Transit Jupiter from the zodiac sign that delay the marriage to be happened is third, fourth, sixth, eighth, tenth and twelfth positions.

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